

EFFICACY OF TERBINAFINE AND ITRACONAZOLE IN PEDIATRIC TINEA INFECTIONS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Dermatophytoses are among the most common fungal infections in children, with increasing incidence and emerging antifungal resistance.

Background:

Dermatophytoses are among the most common fungal infections in children, with increasing incidence and emerging antifungal resistance.

Objective:

To compare the clinical and mycological efficacy of terbinafine and itraconazole in pediatric patients with tinea infections.

Methods:

A randomized, open-label, parallel-group study was conducted in 81 children aged 4–14 years with clinically and mycologically confirmed dermatophytosis. Patients were divided into two groups: terbinafine (n=40) and itraconazole (n=41). Treatment duration was 4 weeks with follow-up at 8 weeks. Outcomes included clinical cure, mycological cure, and recurrence rates. Statistical analysis included chi-square test, relative risk (RR), and odds ratio (OR).

Results:

At 8 weeks, clinical cure was achieved in 70% of patients in the terbinafine group and 78% in the itraconazole group. Mycological cure rates were 72% and 80%, respectively. The relative risk for clinical cure with itraconazole was 1.11 (95% CI: 0.85–1.45), and the odds ratio was 1.52 (95% CI: 0.60–3.85). Recurrence rates were lower in the itraconazole group (10%) compared to terbinafine (15%).

Conclusion:

Both terbinafine and itraconazole are effective treatments for pediatric dermatophytosis. Itraconazole demonstrated a consistent trend toward higher efficacy and lower recurrence rates, although differences were not statistically significant.